

METHODS AND MEANS OF ARTISTIC DECORATION

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Abstract. In this article, we have provided information about the types of national ornaments of the Uzbek people. And we organized the history of their development.

Key words: national, practical, style embroidery, beadwork, goldsmithing, art.

Uzbek folk decorative art is one of the ancient art forms and has been famous all over the world since time immemorial. Painting, which is a component of practical decorative art, occupies a deep place in people's hearts with its antiquity, beauty and charm. Pattern compositions resulting from the mutual harmony of Islamic and Hanseatic pattern elements in a symbolic sense give beauty to practical works of art. There are specific methods of creating a composition in painting, and these pattern decorations show the philosophical worldviews of the masters, their visions of beauty. Each of us understands national heritage in our own way. For tourists, it is the memory of the ancient state, for business guests it is diversity and originality, and for most citizens, it is traditions.

Since childhood, the people of Uzbekistan live in a special environment where bright colors are common and the variety of patterns is amazing. Decoration reigns everywhere here. It can be seen everywhere: in the interior, in the patterns of memorial monuments, in the design of dishes, clothes, bed linen. In the culture of Central Asia, needle-embroidered sheets are of great importance. A fourteen-year-old girl begins to sew a large two-meter suzana for her wedding day. The Uzbek wedding bed is called "gulkurpa" and is decorated with a

blooming garden. In order to have someone in the family to continue the embroidery, one curl should always be unfinished. However, embroidered patterns differ with their specific characteristics in different regions of Uzbekistan. For example, in Samarkand, you can see a bright red rosette with leaves wrapped in rings, and the pattern of the Bukhara suzani made of Bukhara rosettes is similar to the ancient Sogda blankets with the sun sign, where the whole area is perceived as the universe.

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There is a creative union of religion and culture in the national ornament, which creates a magical mano that reflects the course of human life. Today, the classic decorative design is a lush, blooming garden. Fragrant and bright flowers migrated from gardens and steppes to the canvas thanks to the skill and imagination of folk artists. Each flower has its own meaning: the boy is field corn, the girl is red poppy, the rose represents peace and beauty, and the tulip represents innocence and purity. Each of us understands national heritage in our own way. For tourists, it is the memory of the ancient state, for business guests it is diversity and originality, and for most citizens, it is traditions. Since childhood, the people of Uzbekistan live in a special environment where bright colors are common and the variety of patterns is amazing. Decoration reigns everywhere here. It can be seen everywhere: in the interior, in the patterns of architectural monuments, in the design of dishes, clothes, bed linen.

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embroidery, one curl should always be unfinished. However, embroidered patterns differ in their characteristics in different regions of Uzbekistan. For example, in Samarkand, you can see a bright red rosette with leaves wrapped in rings, and the pattern of the Bukhara suzani made of Bukhara rosettes is similar to the ancient Sogda blankets with the sun sign, where the whole area is perceived as the universe.

If you want to see something special, pay attention to the bright diamond-shaped decorations of khan-atlas, which you cannot get out of your head or confuse with anything. There is a creative union of religion and culture in the national ornament, which creates a magical mano that reflects the course of human life. Today, the classic decorative design is a lush, blooming garden. Fragrant and bright flowers migrated from gardens and steppes to the canvas thanks to the skill and imagination of folk artists. Each flower has its own meaning: the boy is field corn, the girl is red poppy, the rose represents peace and beauty, and the tulip represents innocence and purity. Each curl in the decoration has a meaning. In ancient times, embroiderers flowed in separate elements and left whole letters on the material, which hides the secret and spirit of the era. For example, if they want to wish for health or wealth, the decoration is decorated with almonds or ripe pomegranate seeds to protect them from evil, pepper pods, and among the thick leaves, blossoming buds and elegant vines depict bright birds, which represent family happiness. Centuries-old traditions have developed in such a way that clothes are always decorated with national motifs. Women's clothes were filled with necklaces and amulets, with the help of which it was possible to determine her marital status. And doppi was a mandatory headgear for a man, because it was believed to protect against evil spirits. Decorative arts is a branch of decorative arts. Decoration of the street, square, area of enterprises, public buildings, parks on holidays or on any occasion for a certain period of

time, giving artistic spirit to demonstrations, entertainments, various public celebrations; as well as exposition, showcase, stand and city decoration. B. uses the tools of architecture, fine art, theater art, photography, lighting techniques to create the most public examples of the harmony of arts. If the decoration is made of durable raw materials (stone, metal, ceramics, reinforced concrete) in the art of mahogany, then it is made as attractive and simple as possible to the extent that it is temporary, but has an aesthetic effect. In B., each work, each appearance should be unique.

In European countries, in some countries of the East (especially China, Japan), the art of decoration as a field of art was formed and developed in connection with the history of folk dances, religious ceremonies, various celebrations and demonstrations. During the Renaissance in Europe, the role of decorators increased (famous artists such as Leonardo da Vinci, P. Rubens were also effective in the field of decorative arts). In Russia, from the time of Peter I, special decorative artists were involved in palace celebrations. During the celebrations of the French Revolution and the Paris Commune, the art of decoration became a tool of political propaganda. In the 20th century, the role of technology increased in B., especially in the widely used department of electrical engineering, special attention was paid to the improvement of decoration methods in museum and exhibition expositions. B. s is used more for commercial purposes, it serves as a tool of struggle for peace, social development and democracy.

Decoration art has existed in Uzbekistan since ancient times. According to historical sources and manuscripts, the walls of large palaces were decorated with magnificent paintings, which served as both decoration and propaganda. Even in the Middle Ages, the art of Bezash was highly developed in the territory of Uzbekistan. The spirit of this art is reflected in Samarkand, Bukhara, Khiva and other architectural monuments. Masters of decorative art of Uzbekistan develop national traditions and effectively use modern decoration methods (for example,

Independence Day of Uzbekistan, Nowruz holiday, etc.).

Embroidery, embroidery is a profession of embroidery, a branch of applied art. one of the fields. Archeological findings show the antiquity of embroidery in almost all nations, and the development of culture, art, and professions of each nation under the influence of climate, natural conditions, and time. The appearance of embroidery is related to the appearance of seams and stitches in leather clothing. Over time, with the transition from stone to bone beads, from metal beads, as well as weaving, weaving, dyeing, etc. related to work. Qad. It can be observed in the image of embroidery in cultural monuments of Asia, Europe, America, literary sources, as well as in preserved examples of embroidery. The oldest of embroidery products. copies are not kept. In nations where embroidery has developed, it was greatly influenced by fine art. Battle scenes are depicted in English embroidery from the 11th century. Russian embroidery of the 12th century clearly shows the influence of Byzantine icon art. Known as "xiuhua" (needle painting) in China since the 14th century, the embroidered motifs are stylistically close to the genre of silk dreamscapes.

Goldsmithing is a type of decorative art; a branch of applied art that creates ornaments by embroidering with gold (gold and silver) thread, fine wire, and silk. Velvet, silk, movut, leather, etc., mounted on a square belt (korchop). embroidery (flower, pattern, picture) is sewn on fabrics in the zardozi method. Sometimes metal, stone, glass beads are also used in embroidery, they are made of various fabrics (velvet, silk, etc.). Pre-made (copy of the sculpture created by artists) paper is widely used. The paper reinforced (stitched or glued) to the fabric is sewn by covering it with a thread on one side (for the strengthening seam, an oil-colored thread is used for the thread), as a result, the surface of the pattern is covered with threads, and only the shape of the pattern is formed on the reverse side of the fabric. Goldsmiths use several methods to create ornaments: zardozi

zamindozi and zardozi guldozi, as well as birishimdozi (when silk is used), pulakdozi (when button-like metal leaves are used), etc. The skillful use of several types of reinforcing and editing seams and their combination with the embodiment of the pattern gives charm and sophistication to gold jewelry; their artistic value depends on the embodiment of the pattern, raw materials, stitching, and the taste and skill of the goldsmith. A widespread tradition in the embodiment of pattern 3. as a type of artistic craft is widespread in the Near and Middle East. Mainly, items that decorate the interior of buildings, women's holiday dresses are made with 3. Archeological findings and historical manuscripts show that among the peoples of Central Asia, goldsmithing of clothes and artistic items has been developed since ancient times. In his memoirs, the Spanish ambassador Clavijo writes with pleasure about the quilts sewn in the 3rd method, expensive curtains and tents sewn on silk fabric, men's and women's clothes sewn on thread. Abdurazzoq Samarkandi in his pamphlet "Hindistan Safarnoma" recorded that Shahrukh (1442) presented him with a golden hat through the ambassadors he sent to the ruler of the Calcutta region of India. In his treatises, Vasify spoke about his 3. profession. In fact, in the 15th-18th centuries, Bukhara, Samarkand, and Herat rose to a high level. Its development in the 19th century is related to Bukhara. The 3. profession, which is preserved in Bukhara, has been polished and improved over a long period of time. 3. was mainly done by men (now it is also common among women), they worked together in workshops. In the middle of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, almost all of the zardozi items (such as tunics, waistcoats, jackets, pants, shoes, belts, turbans, hats, and jul) were made for the emir and his family, courtiers, and some of the orders of wealthy houses were also fulfilled. . In the 30s and 60s of the 19th century, the more simple the sculptures depicted in Z. were, the smoother and more attractive the embroidery - flowers. In the 70s and 80s of the 19th century, silk thread (pink, crimson, blue, green) woven with a mixture of zar thread was used. Z.'s special

type called zardozi birishimdozi is characteristic of this period. From 1893, new varieties of darning thread were produced in large quantities, displacing colored silk threads and radically changing the general style of sewing.

3. jewelry of the 1890s and 1900s is distinguished by its delicacy. Embossed gyrikhs, stars, and other similar decorations of different shapes give the item a unique look, especially the davqur sculpture has a special place. In the 20s of the 20th century, all the types of practical items changed, the previous luxurious items were replaced by elegantly made items that met the requirements of the time, the embodiment of the pattern was simplified, and the traditional patterns were enriched with forms expressing the spirit of the time. Goldsmiths began to make festive dresses for women (dresses, nimcha, caps, belts, kavush, bags), traditional items, gift dresses and caps for men.

In conclusion, modern Uzbekistan can be proud of its ancient history. Amazingly beautiful ornaments hide centuries-old secrets and reflect the poetic spirit of the Uzbek people.

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